

A Study on Customer Perception towards HDFC Limited

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Abstract—A home loan is a long term commitment which is critical. There are lot many banks and financial institutions through which one can easily avail a home loan. Using customer view assessment and evaluation, various housing finance establishments can focus on the issues most important to the customer and understand points of service strength and weaknesses as viewed by the customer. Consequently, the housing finance sector, as a whole, can develop pertinent service-oriented performance measures and improve the quality of the service offered to society to levels consistent with customer expectation. The study aims at studying the customers' perception on the home loans offered by HDFC Limited, the factors influencing customers in choosing a housing finance agency, reasons for pre closure of home loans and customers' opinion about the Electronic Clearing Service of HDFC Limited. The study is based on descriptive research and follows convenience sampling with a sample size of 150. Primary data is used in the study which is collected through a structured questionnaire. On a majority, the customers agree that the people's service, products and processes are effective. The company can improve the service of updating repayments and conveying information about RBI guidelines and interest rate changes by enabling automatic generated SMS or e-mails to be sent or through tele calling the customers within a time limit of one or two weeks. The major factors that influence customers in choosing housing finance company are competitive interest rate, flexible repayment system, progressive funding and prepayment penalty, which if focused by HDFC can attract new customers and can also retain loyal customers in the long run. Awareness about the home loan products can be created through display boards within the office and newspaper inserts.

Keywords—Housing finance, Perception, Pre closure, Choice

I. INTRODUCTION

A home loan is a long term commitment of 15-20 years, several factors like expertise, quality of service, in-depth domain knowledge and the company's level of commitment and transparency right through, the loan procedures, the fine print, quality of services offered and safe retrieval of the title deed are critical. There are lot many banks and financial institutions through which one can easily avail of a home loan at reasonable rate of

interest. The success of a business depends upon its ability to attract and retain customers that are willing to purchase goods and services at prices that are profitable to the company. Consumer perception describes how customers and potential customers view a company and its products and services. Consumer perception is important to businesses since it can influence consumer behaviour, which ultimately affects the profitability of a business.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Customer perceptions are influenced by a variety of factors. Besides the actual outcome i.e. did the product or service deliver the expected function and did it fulfil the customers need – the whole process of consumption and all interactions involved are of crucial importance. In today's globalised information driven economy this can also comprise issues like:

- How other customers or influencing groups perceive the product or brand
- The degree to which the customer feels the actual marketing campaign addresses the most important issues
- Responsiveness and service quality of any affiliates, e.g. distribution partners

A. Consumer Perception Process

Fig.1 Consumer Perception Process

Exposure

Exposure, the first step of the perception process, occurs when a stimulus comes within the range of the senses. Exposure is therefore simply the minimum requirement of perception. Exposure to stimuli is of either an intentional or an accidental nature. Intentional exposure occurs when an individual is exposed to market-related information because of his own intentional, goal-directed behaviour, i.e. it reflects a person's interests, reading habits, information needs and life style. Accidental exposure to stimuli occurs when the individual is exposed to intensive marketing campaigns, such as the messages portrayed by the broadcasting media, billboards and the vast number of magazine and newspaper advertisements.

Attention

Attention is of crucial importance, since no matter how often a consumer is exposed to marketing stimuli, if no attention takes place, the message is of no use. Attention to a given stimulus has taken place only if a consumer notices or attends to the stimulus.

Organisation

People do not experience the numerous stimuli they select from the environment as separate and discrete sensations. They rather tend to organise them into groups and perceive them as unified wholes.

Interpretation

Interpretation is a process whereby people draw upon their experience, memory, and expectations to interpret and attach meaning to stimulus. The interpretation phase is uniquely individual, since it is based upon what individuals expect to see in the light of their previous experience, on the number of plausible explanations they can envision, and on their interests and motives at the time perception occurs.

Retention

Retention is the process by which the consumers remember the stimulus that they have noticed and interpreted through their experiences. Consumers retain the memory that they have gained through their attention and prepare to focus on it.

Purchase and Consumption Decision

The purchase decision depends on considerations such as terms of sale, past experience buying from the seller and return policy. It will be also influenced by the atmosphere, time pressure, a sale and pleasantness of the experience.

B. Aspects of Measuring Customer Perceptions

First of all the company has to find out how it and its offerings are perceived by the customers. This information is of greater value if it can be compared to the customers' perception of competitive offerings. Not only will this reveal relative strengths and weaknesses, it is also a valuable source of ideas for improvement. Besides that, surveys should also identify the relative importance of several influencing variables in the eyes of

the customer. To know what matters most to the customer helps to set priorities for projects. It should be based on careful customer segmentation. Customer groups that differ by frequency of use, social status, geographical region or other criteria, are likely to have different expectations and preferences. Hence, they will probably perceive an offering in different ways.

C. The 3 P's in driving Customer Perception

In every organization, regardless of the industry it belongs to and its nature of business, there are three key factors that influence customer's perception towards the

People

As any customer service front line would agree, the "People" element is viewed as the most important factor in driving customer perception. Front liners such as the Contact Centre and Sales Agents are the ambassadors of the organizations. The actions they take; the choices of words they use when interacting with customers; the behavior they display when handling customers, would affect the customer's perception towards the organization.

Process

In order to function in a structured and manageable manner, organizations cannot avoid but to put in place different processes, which include policies and procedures. Whenever an organization intends to change or revise its processes, the first thing is to think in the customer's shoes.

D. Benefits of a Customer Perception Study

- It enables fact-based decision making about the business
- Helps understand what customers like about the company and why
- Identifies opportunities for improvement
- Prioritises changes based on customer feedback
- Strengthens customer relationships
- Measures effectiveness of advertising and PR programmes
- Develops a focused and effective communications programme
- Benchmarks against the competitors

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

John Mylonakis (2007) in his study on "A Research Study of Customer Preferences in the Home Loans Market: The Mortgage Experience of Greek Bank Customers", concluded that the important influential factors emerge, such as the various offers of banks, the bank's reputation, existing cooperation, as well as bank staff. Bank branches proved to continue constituting the

organization. Coincidentally all of them start with the letter "P" – Product, People and Process.

Product

The types of products and/ or services offered by an organization will affect customer's perception and experience. In this dynamic business world, organization needs to evolve constantly and continuously in meeting customer's needs. In organizations that constantly strive to offer products and/ or services that meet customers' demands, the Marketing or in some cases, also the R&D department plays a vital role.

primary distribution channel for mortgage products and services.

D. Regis Arunodayam and N. Thangavel (2007) in their study on "A study of the Housing Industry with special reference to the city of Chennai" examined the developments in the housing finance in India in the early 21st century and the magnitude of the problem of housing in the country and the implication of housing policies.

Kirti Dutta and Anil Dutta (2009) in their study on "Customer Expectations and Perceptions across the Indian Banking Industry and the Resultant Financial Implications" have studied the expectations and perceptions of the consumers across the three banking sectors in India. It was found that in the banking sector it is the foreign banks which are perceived to be offering better quality of services followed by the private and then public banks and these perceptions are reflected in the financial performance of the banks also.

Aparna Mishra and Kamini Tandon (2011) in their study on "A Customer Centric Approach towards Retail Banking Services: A Glimpse" analyzed the customers' perception on the retail banking services offered by namely five private sector banks situated in Delhi and to study the major factors influencing their choice of banks and its products.

Rashmi Chaudhary and Yasmin Janjhua (2011) in their study on "Customer Perceptions and Satisfaction towards Home Loans" found that the customers of the bank were highly satisfied with the home loan services in relation to its services, transparency, time taken for loan approval, employee co-operation and query handling, prima facie of some problems like procedural delays, lack of knowledge and red-tapism.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To analyze the customers' perception on home loans offered by HDFC Ltd.,
- To study the factors influencing the customers' choice of housing finance companies

- To study the reasons for pre closure of home loans by customers at HDFC Ltd.,
- To study the customers' opinion about Electronic Clearing Service of HDFC Ltd.,

V. RESEARCH DESIGN

The type of research design used here is the descriptive research. Descriptive research is carried out to describe the characteristics of consumer segment viz., demographic, socio-economic, geographic, psychographic and benefits sought.

A. Sampling Technique

The sampling technique used in this research is convenience sampling. Convenience sampling is a non probability sampling technique where subjects are

selected because of their convenient accessibility and proximity to the researcher. The sample size is 150.

B. Method of Data Collection

The study depends on primary data. A structured questionnaire is used for collection of data.

VI. RESEARCH GAP

The existing researches dealt with the studying of customer perception towards banking services and insurance industry. So far, not many studies have been carried out on the customer perception towards home loans. Hence the research has been carried out to study the customers' perception on home loans.

VII. TOOLS USED

The tools that are used are Percentage analysis, Factor analysis, Chi-square analysis and Mean score.

VIII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

TABLE I. DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Gender	No. of respondents	Percentage
Male	122	81.3
Female	28	18.7
Total	150	100
Age (in yrs)	No. of respondents	Percentage
25 – 35	41	27.3
35 – 45	51	34.0
45 – 55	43	28.7
55 – 65	15	10.0
Total	150	100
Educational Qualification	No. of respondents	Percentage
Up to Class 12	30	20.0
Diploma	19	12.7
Graduate	50	33.3
Post Graduate	50	33.3
Others	1	0.7
Total	150	100
Occupation	No. of respondents	Percentage
Salaried	101	67.3
Self-Employed	26	17.3
Others	23	15.3
Total	150	100
Marital Status	No. of respondents	Percentage
Married	133	88.7
Unmarried	17	11.3
Total	150	100
Monthly Income (in	No. of respondents	Percentage
15,000-35,000	61	40.7
35,000-55,000	28	18.7

55,000-75,000	22	14.7
More than 75,000	31	20.7
Others	8	5.3
Total	150	100
Location	No. of	Percentage
Urban	86	57.3
Semi-urban	31	20.7
Semi-rural	16	10.7
Rural	17	11.3
Total	150	100

Majority (81.3%) of the respondents are male. Most (34.0%) of the respondents belong to the age group 35 to 45 years. Most (33.3%) of the respondents are graduates and post graduates each. Majority (67.3%) of the respondents belong to the salaried class. Majority (88.7%) of the respondents are married. Most (40.7%) of the respondents earn an income between Rs. 15,000 and Rs. 35,000 per month. Majority (57.3%) of the respondents reside in urban locations.

TABLE II. **DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON THE CUSTOMERS' ASSOCIATION WITH HDFC**

Association with HDFC as a	No. of respondents	Percentage
Less than 5	66	44.0
5-10	49	32.7
10-15	26	17.3
More than 15	9	6.0
Total	150	100

Most (44.4%) of the respondents are associated with HDFC for less than 5 years. 32.7% of the respondents are associated with HDFC for around 5 to 10 years, 17.3% of the respondents are associated with HDFC for around 10 to 15 years and 6.0% of the respondents are associated with HDFC for more than 15 years.

TABLE III. **DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON THE HOME LOAN PRODUCT TAKEN**

Home Loan Product	No. of	Percent
Home Loan for Construction	76	50.7
Home Improvement Loan	22	14.7
Home Extension Loan	14	9.3
Top-up Loan	6	4.0
Equity Loan	6	4.0
Plot Loan	8	5.3
Loan for NRI	10	6.3
Loan for Non-residential premises	1	0.7
Home Improvement Loan and Top-up Loan	1	0.7
Home Extension Loan and Top-up Loan	2	1.3
Home Loan for Construction and Home Extension Loan	2	1.3
Home Loan for Construction and Loan for NRI	1	0.7
Home Improvement Loan and Home Extension Loan	1	0.7

Total	150	100
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Most (50.7%) of the respondents have taken a home loan for construction. 14.7% of the respondents have taken a home improvement loan, 9.3% of the respondents have taken a home extension loan, 6.7% of the respondents have taken a loan under NRI category, 5.3% of the respondents have taken a plot loan, 4.0% of the respondents have taken a top-up loan and equity loan respectively.

TABLE IV. DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON THE MODE OF REPAYMENT OF LOAN

Mode of repayment	No. of	Percentage
PDC	40	26.7
ECS	107	71.3
BSI	3	2.0
Total	150	100

Majority (71.3%) of the respondents repay their EMI through ECS. 26.7% of the respondents repay through PDCs and 2.0% of the respondents repay through BSI.

Relationship between customers' association with HDFC and customers' perception based on the people factor

This part of the analysis deals with the relationship between the customers' association with HDFC and the customers' perception on the people factor (human resources) of HDFC. For this purpose the following hypothesis is formed.

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between the customers' association with HDFC and their perception on the people factor (human resources).

H_a : There is significant relationship between the customers' association with HDFC and their perception on the people factor (human resources).

TABLE V. CHI-SQUARE TEST ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CUSTOMERS' ASSOCIATION WITH HDFC AND THE PEOPLE FACTOR

Factors	Chi-square value	'p'	Result
Courteousness	7.260 ^a	0.840	Accepted
Communication in	9.671 ^a	0.645	Accepted
Expertise	12.370 ^a	0.416	Accepted
Guidance	15.275 ^a	0.227	Accepted
Explanations on terms and	12.943 ^a	0.373	Accepted
Readiness to meet customers	16.138 ^a	0.185	Accepted
Behavior post sanction/	12.709 ^a	0.391	Accepted
Query handling	9.750 ^a	0.638	Accepted
Overall service	6.210 ^a	0.905	Accepted

Relationship between customers' association with HDFC and customers' perception based on the product factor

This part of the analysis deals with the relationship between the customers' association with HDFC and the product factor considered for perception. For this purpose the following hypothesis is formed.

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between the customers' association with HDFC and their perception on the products.

H_a : There is significant relationship between the customers' association with HDFC and their perception on the products.

TABLE VI. CHI-SQUARE TEST ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CUSTOMERS' ASSOCIATION WITH HDFC AND THE PRODUCT FACTOR

Factors	Chi-square	'P'	Result
Variety of home loan	5.177 ^a	0.952	Accepted
Competitive	14.515 ^a	0.269	Accepted
Reasonable processing fees	13.864 ^a	0.309	Accepted
Flexible	18.241 ^a	0.109	Accepted
Flexible tenure	7.633 ^a	0.813	Accepted
Availability of prepayment	9.804 ^a	0.367	Accepted

Relationship between customers' association with HDFC and customers' perception based on the process factor

This part of the analysis deals with the relationship between the customers' association with HDFC and the process factor considered for perception. For this purpose the following hypothesis is formed.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the customers' association with HDFC and their perception on the process.

H_a: There is significant relationship between the customers' association with HDFC and their perception on the process.

TABLE VII. CHI-SQUARE TEST ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CUSTOMERS' ASSOCIATION WITH HDFC AND THE PROCESS FACTOR

Factors	Chi-square value	'P'	Result
Reasonable documentation and legal formalities	9.170 ^a	0.688	Accepted
Transparency	11.667 ^a	0.473	Accepted
Faster processing	7.010 ^a	0.857	Accepted
Reasonable lobby waiting time	5.828 ^a	0.925	Accepted
Quicker sanctioning	10.213 ^a	0.597	Accepted
Disbursements at the right time	11.674 ^a	0.472	Accepted
Prompt and accurate updation of repayment	16.053 ^a	0.189	Accepted
Return of deleted cheques within specified time	14.740 ^a	0.256	Accepted
Provision of statements at the right time	5.559 ^a	0.937	Accepted
Release of documents on due dates	12.381 ^a	0.416	Accepted

Factors influencing the customers' choice of housing finance agency

TABLE VIII. KMO AND BARTLETT'S TEST

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.863
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1.101E3
	Df	136
	Sig.	.000

TABLE IX. COMMUNALITIES

TABLE X.

Factors	Initial	Extraction
Low rate of interest	1.000	0.525
Faster processing	1.000	0.750
Minimal formalities and procedures	1.000	0.644
Flexible repayment system	1.000	0.707
Convenient repayment term	1.000	0.646
Prepayment penalty	1.000	0.718
Progressive funding	1.000	0.636
In-house legal and technical services	1.000	0.631
Home Insurance	1.000	0.367
Lesser miscellaneous charges	1.000	0.558
Professional customer service	1.000	0.672
Influence of sales people	1.000	0.543
Service pre-sanction and post-sanction	1.000	0.709
Influence of friends and relatives	1.000	0.443
Brand name of the housing finance agency	1.000	0.605
Influence of advertisements	1.000	0.703
Location and ambience of the housing finance agency	1.000	0.699

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.320	37.175	37.175	6.320	37.175	37.175
2	2.095	12.326	49.501	2.095	12.326	49.501
3	1.105	6.498	55.999	1.105	6.498	55.999

4	1.036	6.095	62.094	1.036	6.095	62.094
5	.869	5.112	67.206			
6	.792	4.656	71.862			
7	.677	3.983	75.845			
8	.645	3.793	79.638			
9	.627	3.689	83.327			
10	.561	3.303	86.630			
11	.450	2.647	89.277			
12	.444	2.609	91.886			
13	.342	2.012	93.898			
14	.336	1.976	95.875			
15	.274	1.614	97.489			
16	.256	1.503	98.992			
17	.171	1.008	100.000			

TABLE XI. ROTATED COMPONENT MATRIX^A

Factors	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Low rate of interest	.651	.130	-.023	.289
Faster processing	.180	.233	.053	.813
Minimal formalities and procedures	.183	.059	.066	.776
Flexible repayment system	.658	.100	.173	.484
Convenient repayment term	.543	.311	.095	.494
Prepayment penalty	.839	.071	.076	-.054
Progressive funding	.628	.393	.062	.288
In-house legal and technical services	.424	.563	.194	.312
Home Insurance	.365	.414	.239	.067
Lesser miscellaneous charges	.463	.496	.207	.233
Professional customer service	.318	.745	.044	.114
Influence of sales people	-.033	.617	.399	-.054
Service pre-sanction and post-sanction	.057	.745	.183	.342
Influence of friends and relatives	.180	.351	.533	-.063
Brand name of the housing finance agency	.285	.007	.702	.177
Influence of advertisements	-.059	.261	.790	-.088
Location and ambience of the housing finance agency	-.004	.126	.792	.237

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Factors 1

- Prepayment penalty
- Flexible repayment system
- Low rate of interest
- Progressive funding

Factors 2

- Service pre-sanction and post-sanction
- Professional customer service

Factors 3

- Location and ambience of the housing finance agency
- Influence of advertisements
- Brand name of the housing finance agency

Factors 4

- Faster processing
- Minimal formalities and procedures

Reasons for pre closure of home loans

TABLE XII. MEAN SCORE – REASONS FOR PRE CLOSURE OF HOME LOANS

Reasons	Mean score	Rank
High interest rate	3.11	2
Availability of ready funds	2.87	1
Plan for availing new loans	4.37	4
Reduction of financial commitments	4.05	3
Extensive mortgage period	4.44	5
Plan of selling the property	5.51	6
Moving to a different geographic location	6.51	8
Demise of the customer	7.46	10
Change in career	6.54	9
Additional responsibilities (Marriage, Children)	5.91	7

Relationship between customers' demographic profile and their opinion about ECS

This part of the analysis deals with the relationship between the demographic profiles of the respondents with the customers' opinion about ECS. For this purpose the following hypothesis is formed.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the customers' demographic profile and their opinion about ECS.

H_a: There is a significant relationship between the customers' demographic profile and their opinion about ECS.

TABLE XIII. CHI-SQUARE TEST ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CUSTOMERS' DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE AND THEIR OPINION ABOUT ECS

Factors	Chi-square value	'P'	Result
Gender	7.226 ^a	0.300	Accepted
Age	20.168 ^a	0.323	Accepted
Educational Qualification	20.585 ^a	0.663	Accepted
Occupation	7.397 ^a	0.830	Accepted
Marital Status	6.235 ^a	0.397	Accepted
Monthly Income	12.434 ^a	0.824	Accepted
Location	11.013 ^a	0.894	Accepted
Customers' association with HDFC	24.704 ^a	0.133	Accepted

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

On a majority, the customers agree that the people's service, products and processes are effective. The company can improve the service of updating repayments and conveying information about RBI guidelines and interest rate changes by enabling automatic generated SMS or e-mails to be sent or through tele calling the customers within a time limit of one or two weeks. The major factors that influence customers in choosing housing finance company are competitive interest rate, flexible repayment system, progressive funding and prepayment penalty, which if focused by HDFC can attract new customers and can also retain loyal customers in the long run. Awareness about the home loan products can be created through display boards within the office and newspaper inserts.

X. CONCLUSION

The study mainly focuses on studying the customers' perception towards HDFC Ltd., The study is based on descriptive research and follows a convenience sampling technique with a sample size of 150. Findings reveal that the customers perceive the overall service of the employees to be very good on an average. On a majority, the customers agree that the products and processes are also effective. The following suggestions and recommendations are offered based on the knowledge gained during the study and based on the findings of the analysis. The customers felt that there is no proper updation of repayments. The company can improve the service by enabling automatic generated SMS or e-mails to be sent as soon as the entries are made in the loan accounts of the customers in the system. The customers felt that the RBI guidelines and any such changes on interest rates are not properly conveyed to them. The company can improve the service by tele calling, sending SMS and e-mails to the customers regarding the From the factor analysis that had been made, it is observed that the major factors that influence customers in choosing housing finance company are competitive interest rate, flexible repayment system, progressive funding and prepayment penalty. If HDFC keeps focusing on these factors, it can attract new customers and can also retain more loyal customers in the long run. Majority of the customers are not aware of the various other home loan products offered by HDFC, other than the product availed by them. Awareness can be created through display boards within the office and newspaper inserts.

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